

Original Article

Postoperative Keratometric Astigmatism Axis Shift in Cataract Operated Adult Patients in National Eye Centre, Kaduna.

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ABSTRACT

Cataract surgery incisions distort corneal curvature at meridian of incision with tendency to change the orientation of astigmatism. In this article, we determine the pattern of astigmatism types in cataract operated adult patients in National Eye Centre, Kaduna. This was a prospective randomized interventional study involving 150 patients with cataract distributed into three groups for cataract surgery with posterior chamber intraocular lens (PCIOL) implantation. In group I, 41 patients had extracapsular cataract extraction (ECCE), group II, 68 patients had manual small incision cataract surgery (MSICS) by superior incision and group III, 41 patients had manual small incision cataract surgery by temporal incision. The patients were evaluated with autokeratometer for keratometric astigmatism preoperatively, at 1 week and 6 weeks after surgery. Data were analyzed using SPSS Version 16 and P-value less than or equal to 0.05 was considered statistically significant. The preoperative type of astigmatism for each of the groups was similar: WTR; 12(29.3), 21(30.9), 12(29.3), (P 0.99) and ATR; 22(53.7), 34(50.0), 21(51.2), (P 0.91) with predominantly ATR. There was a shift in the type of astigmatism from Against-the-rule (ATR) to With-the-rule astigmatism (WTR) in 29(70.7%) extracapsular cataract surgery and 21(51.2%) manual small incision cataract surgery by temporal incision. Increased Against-the-rule (ATR) in 41(60.3%) manual small incision cataract surgery by superior incision (Msup) was found in the first week after surgery. This pattern was statistically significant at 6 weeks after surgery. Astigmatism is predominantly against the rule in adults but changes depending on the procedure used in cataract operated eyes.

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INTRODUCTION

Cataract accounts for almost half of the causes of blindness and affects an estimated 18 million people with bilateral blindness.¹ The prevalence of cataracts among people 40 years and above in Nigeria is 19.8%.²

Cataract surgery is a cost-effective means of a reversal of cataract blind eyes. It has evolved to recent times, it is being considered refractive surgery aim at achieving excellent uncorrected visual outcome more so when spectacle dependence post cataract surgery is no more fashionable³. The surgery involves creating incisions on the cornea, limbus or sclera to deliver the opacified lens. This causes flattening at the meridian of incision with a corresponding steepening 90° away.⁴ The distortion of the normal contour of the eyeball that follows whether sutured or not impacts on the existence or otherwise of astigmatism. Moderate to severe astigmatism whether it is preexisting or induced by surgery is associated with visual outcome in cataract operated eyes. Imam *et al*⁵ in a national survey in Nigeria reported that in cataract operated patients good vision was found in patients with low astigmatism while high astigmatic error was found in patients with poor vision. Preoperatively, it is estimated at 60% in a study in India⁶ and in Spain⁷ 34.8% of patients had corneal astigmatism of >1.00D.

The association of cataract surgery with astigmatism and astigmatism with visual outcome has therefore made studies on astigmatism in cataract operated eyes necessary considering that literature on the topic is scarce in Nigeria. The surgically induced astigmatism in cataract operated eyes in this study in terms of magnitude in dioptres has been described elsewhere. The present aspect of the study considered the pattern of keratometric astigmatism axis shift in age-related cataract operated adults in National Eye Centre, Kaduna, caused by superior extracapsular cataract extraction, superior manual small incision cataract surgery and temporal small incision cataract surgery.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This is a prospective randomized interventional

hospital-based study carried out among consecutive patients with age-related operable cataract that presented at NEC, Kaduna from 3rd January 2011 to 20th November 2012. Those included were adult patients 40 years and above with uncomplicated age-related cataract that consented to participate in the study. Those excluded were patients with other ocular causes of severe visual loss as; diabetic retinopathy, glaucoma, pterygium, other corneal surface irregularities and past ocular surgeries. Those who had intra-operative complications that may affect the astigmatism as; patients with ACIOL, vitreous loss and those who refused to give their consent.

Approval for the study was obtained from the Ethical Committee of National Eye Centre, Kaduna. The study was carried out in conformity with Helsinki declaration. Written informed consent was obtained from all the patients.

Methods

Doctors in Primary Care Clinic (PCC) referred all patients 40 years and above with cataracts to the researcher. The aim of the study and the procedures involved were explained to the patients. Those who consented and met the inclusion criteria signed consent and were included in the study.

Preoperative evaluation

The biodata including age, sex, occupation, marital status, ethnic group, and religion as well as, the laterality were recorded on a data sheet. The visual acuity (VA) was assessed. Other parameters assessed were pupillary reaction for direct and consensual light reflexes and slit lamp examination to rule out eye lid, or ocular surface irregularities, infections and inflammation. The pupils were dilated using either mydriacyl 1% alone and/or phenylephrine 2.5% to check for the cataract's morphology, maturity and position, the status of the zonules, degree of mydriasis and where possible posterior segment examination. Keratometry was also done to get the baseline

astigmatism in diopters using autokeratometer. The keratometer automatically recorded and displayed the dioptric powers of the central cornea in the vertical and horizontal meridians. It also displayed the difference of the two meridians in magnitude (D) and direction in (degrees) or axis. The average value of 3 readings was used.

A list of all the eligible patients was made, this served as the sampling frame from which, a table of random numbers was used in distributing the patients to the various procedures and surgeons

Intraoperative

The pupils were dilated with either gut tropicamide 1% alone or in addition to gutt phenylephrine 2.5%, before the surgery. Anaesthetic nurses administered peribulbar injection of 5-7 mls of 2% xylocaine with adrenaline to achieve akinesia and then pressure was applied using Honan's balloon for about 8 minutes to achieve adequate hypotony.

On the operating table, the surgeon cleaned the patient's face with 5% povidone iodine and a few drops were instilled into the conjunctival fornices. The face was then draped and the povidone iodine flushed out of the fornices. After which the lids were retracted using lid retractors and bridle sutures passed under the superior rectus to stabilize the globe.

A fornix based conjunctival flap was fashioned and mild bipolar wet field cautery was applied to achieve haemostasis in the 3 procedures.

For conventional ECCE procedure, a groove was made at the superior limbus measuring about 10 mm, the anterior chamber (AC) was entered into by a stab incision at 12 o'clock position and was reformed with viscoelastic. A can opener capsulotomy was done with insulin needle, and the corneal incision completed using universal corneal scissors. The nucleus was then delivered by pressure and counter pressure using vectis and the cortex aspirated using Simcoe cannula. More viscoelastic was injected to reform the AC, the PCIOL was then implanted in the

bag and dialed into position. The viscoelastic was then aspirated and replaced with normal saline. Five interrupted, radially spaced stitches were applied using 10/0 nylon.

In MSICS, the superior incision was centered at 12 o'clock while the temporal incision was centered at 3 or 9 o'clock depending on the eye. After fashioning the conjunctival flap and applying mild bipolar wet field cautery, a straight scleral incision measuring 6-7mm in length at a distance of 2mm from the limbus was made using a blade. A tunnel was then created using a crescent knife extending 2mm into clear cornea.

With a keratome, the AC was entered into superiorly through the tunnel, the AC was reformed with viscoelastic, a bent insulin needle was introduced through the same site and a can-opener capsulotomy was made. Thereafter, the keratome was used again to extend the entry wound into the AC to the sides nasally and temporally. The AC was then reformed with viscoelastic and hydrodissection done. The nucleus was prolapsed into the AC using Sinskey's hook and lens delivered by visco expression. Simcoe cannula was used to aspirate cortical matter and more viscoelastic injected to reform the AC. The PCIOL was then implanted into the capsular bag and dialed into position when necessary. The viscoelastic was aspirated using Simcoe cannula. For all patients, subconjunctival injection of dexamethasone 4mg and gentamicine 20mg was given. This was followed by instillation of a drop of topical dexamethasone 0.1%, chloramphenicol and mydriacy 1%. The eyes were then padded. On the first postoperative day, the eye pads were removed and the eyes cleaned under aseptic technique with normal saline. Thereafter, visual acuity assessment and slit lamp examination were carried out on the operated eye of each patient. The patients were placed on topical dexamethasone qds, chloramphenicol qds, 0.5% tropicamide bd for 4-6 weeks and tablet cataflam 50mg bd for 7 days. The patients were discharged on the second day after surgery.

Follow up

Follow up was carried out on the 7th day and 6th week postsurgery. At each follow up, the VA and detailed slit lamp, fundal examination and keratometry were carried out by the investigator.

Power of the study - 80%

Sample size - 150

Using formula $n = Z^2 \alpha / 2 P (1-p) / d^2$

$(1.65) \times (1.65) \times 0.5(1-0.5) / (0.08) \times (0.08)$

$3.8416 \times 0.025 / 0.0064 = 150$

Sample Size

Prevalence- 50% (p=0.50). This is because at the time of study design, no crude prevalence was available from a Nigerian study.

Confidence interval - 95%

Desired precision (δ) - 0.08 (8%)

Data Analysis

Data collected was analyzed using SPSS version 16 after manual cleaning and coding, Chi- square test and ANOVA was used to test for associations. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Table 1. Preoperative characteristics of the patients

Characteristic considered	Total (%)	ECCE (%)	Msup (%)	Mtem (%)	P value
Number of eyes	150	41 (27.33)	68 (45.33)	41 (27.33)	
Mean age (years)	61.82	60.68	61.06	64.2	0.230
Sex					
Males	86(100)	29(33.7)	36(41.9)	21(24.4)	
Females	64(100)	12(18.8)	32(50.0)	20(31.3)	0.124
Laterality					
Right eye	82(100)	24(29.3)	36(43.9)	22(26.8)	
Left eye	68(100)	17(25.0)	32(47.1)	19(27.9)	0.84

Table 2. Distribution of preoperative types of astigmatism in ECCE, Msup and Mtem groups.

Type of Astigmatism	Type of surgery			Total (%)	P value (chi square test)
	ECCE (%)	Msup (%)	Mtem (%)		
WTR	12(29.3)	21(30.9)	12(29.3)	45(30.0)	0.99
ATR	22(53.7)	34(50.0)	21(51.2)	77(51.2)	0.91
OBL	3(7.2)	4(5.9)	2(4.87)	9(6.0)	0.90
NEU	4(9.8)	9(13.2)	6(14.6)	19(12.7)	0.73
TOTAL	41(100)	68(100)	41(100)	150(100)	

In this study, 150 eyes of 150 patients were operated on, 68 eyes had MSICS, superior incision, 41 eyes MSICS temporal incision (Mtem) and 41 for ECCE. The age of patients ranged from 40-88 years with a mean of 61.82 years ±10.68SD. Eighty six (57.3%) were males and 64(42.3 %) females. Eighty two patients (54.7%) had cataract surgery in the right eyes while 68 (45.3%) in the left respectively.

The type of astigmatism was also not statistically significant between the groups preoperatively (WTR p= 0.99, ATR p=0.91, NEUTRA p= 0.73) as shown in table 2.

First postoperative week

All the 150 patients came for follow up on the first postoperative week.

Pattern of astigmatism.

WTR astigmatism was found in the first week of the surgery in 29(70.73%), 19(27.9%) and 21(51.22%) of patients that were offered ECCE, Msup and Mtem respectively. In addition, there were 9(22.00%), 41(60.33%) and 14(34.15%) of ATR for ECCE, Msup and Mtem respectively. These were statistically significant as shown in table 3. The remaining eyes had neutral or oblique astigmatism.

The sixth postoperative week

One hundred and forty- eight (98.67%) patients attended follow up in the 6th postoperative week. Two (1.33%) patients were lost to follow up while 1 patient (0.67%) had incomplete clinical data.

Table 3.Type of astigmatism by surgery type at 1 week of surgery.

Type of Astigmatism	Type of surgery			Total (%)	P value (chi square test)
	ECCE (%)	Msup (%)	Mtem (%)		
WTR	29(70.7)	19(27.9)	21(51.2%)	69(46.0)	0.000
ATR	9(22.0)	41(60.3)	14(34.2)	64(42.7)	0.000
OBL	3(7.3)	4(5.9)	0(0)	7(4.6)	0.359
NEU	0(0)	4(5.9)	6(14.6)	10(6.7)	0.104
TOTAL	41(100)	68(100)	34(100)	150(100)	

Table 4.The pattern of astigmatism by type of surgery at 6 weeks of surgery.

Type of Astigmatism	Type of surgery			Total (%)	P value (chi square test)
	ECCE (%)	Msup (%)	Mtem (%)		
WTR	21(60.0)	23(34.3)	13(38.2)	57(41.9)	0.035
ATR	9(25.7)	35(52.2)	16(47.1)	60(44.1)	0.049
OBL	5(14.3)	5(7.5)	1(2.9)	11(8.1)	0.295
NEU	0(00.0)	4(6.0)	4(11.8)	8(5.9)	0.104
TOTAL	35(100)	67(100)	34(100)	136(100)	

DISCUSSION

Cataract surgery has advanced from couching to modern day small incision Phacoemulsification and more recently femto second laser assisted surgery leading to rapid visual recovery, wound healing and control of astigmatism. In our setting, cataract surgery has not advanced to the level of sutureless sub-3mm phaco-incisions placed on step meridians to control preexisting and minimize induced astigmatism but routinely offer MSICS and ECCE in superior, oblique and temporal positions. Consequently, causing varied degrees of astigmatism. Corneal astigmatism is often classified according to the axis as being either against the rule (ATR) when horizontal meridian is steepest, with-the rule (WTR) when vertical meridian is steepest or oblique when the steepest meridian lies between 120-150 and 30-60 degrees.⁸ We therefore describe the axis shift of astigmatism in ATR, WTR, Oblique and Neutral based on approach to cataract surgery obtainable in our setting, MSICS and ECCE.

In this study, we found in the preoperative 77(51.3%) ATR, 45(30.0%) WTR, 9(6.0%) Oblique and 19 (12.7%) Neutral, indicating in cataract age group 40 and above in our environment, astigmatism is mostly ATR and is consistent with report that ATR astigmatism is the major type of astigmatism in old age. The cornea in most instances is not a perfect sphere and radius of curvature is not the same in the horizontal and vertical meridians. It is steeper vertically than horizontally in childhood while the reverse is the case in adulthood.⁹ Therefore, children tend to have WTR astigmatism. The shift in pattern with age has been suggested to be due to the upper and lower lids compressing a portion of the cornea and causing steepening of the vertical curvature leading to WTR astigmatism in the young. This compressive effect of the lids is lessened by lid laxity, decreased tone of Muller's muscle and increased corneal rigidity with aging.¹⁰

In preoperative state, the types of astigmatism were similar in all the 3 groups; ATR, p 0.99 and WTR, p 0.91 but one week after surgery, there were significant changes; ATR, p 0.00 and WTR, p 0.00. Suggesting the different surgical procedures was responsible. There was an increase in the number of eyes with ATR in Msup 41(60.33%), as well as an increase in the number of eyes with WTR in Mtem 21(51.2%) and 29(70.7%) in ECCE as shown in tables 2 and 3. The surgical incisions caused flattening at their meridian with a corresponding steepening 90° away⁴ and the meridian of steepening defines the type of astigmatism.

When these incisions are sutured like in ECCE, the sutures may be loose and behave like sutureless wounds or be tight a more likely outcome in most surgery because of need to stabilize large incisions till wound healing takes place. The tighter sutures produce more tension that compresses the meridian of the suture causing an increase steepness and thereby astigmatism. In this study, the superior incisions were sutured this increased steepness in the superior meridian and lead to WTR astigmatism shift. Luntz et al¹¹ reported high 3-10 D, WTR at the initial stage of surgery caused by tight sutures while working on astigmatism in cataract surgery.

In this study, suture less wounds in two different locations were found to cause different types of astigmatic shift, the major type of astigmatism in superior group ATR 41(60.3%) and temporal incision WTR 21(51.2%). Similarly, a study compared the type of postoperative astigmatism in Sudan and found a significant change to WTR astigmatism after temporal clear corneal incision and to against the rule (ATR) astigmatism in the superior scleral SICS. The difference was attributed to the distractive force of eyelid blinking on superior wound. This agrees with Oshika¹³ that there is a slight ATR shift in superior incision, and a slight WTR shift in temporal incisions.

Again this study found that incisions at the same location cause different types of astigmatic changes when sutured and unsutured; superior ECCE WTR 29(70.7%) and superior MSICS ATR 41(60.3%). Sood *et al*¹⁴ showed that conventional ECCE and sutureless ECCE (MSICs) aside from difference in magnitude of astigmatism, the type of astigmatic axis shift was also different. ECCE had WTR 72%, neutral 7.8% but for MSICS WTR was 40%, ATR 40% and neutral 20%. This has shown that suturing or none suturing of wounds does not only affect the magnitude but also the pattern of astigmatism. This is better demonstrated by the report of Luntz *et al*¹¹ that by cutting sutures in superior wounds with high astigmatism there was a rapid change from WTR to ATR. When absorbable sutures are used in cataract surgery they lose their apparent strength early leading to a rapid change in the pattern of astigmatism from WTR to ATR.

In the postoperative period, remodeling of healing wounds causes a gradual shift from the immediate postoperative astigmatism both in magnitude and axis. However, the duration of this shift has been reported to extend to about 1 year but wounds are considered stable enough for spectacle correction of refractive error at 6 weeks. In this stable state at 6 weeks the postoperative astigmatism pattern change was still noticeable; WTR (p 0.035), ATR (p 0.049) in the 3 groups in this study.

CONCLUSION

Cataract surgery leads to a change in pattern of astigmatism, this is noticeable at 6 weeks of surgery.

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